

CHEMICAL ADDICTION IN ADOLESCENTS: PSYCHOPROPHYLAXIS AND REHABILITATION THROUGH ART THERAPY

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ANNOTATION: Relevance. The increasing use of psychoactive substances (PAS), particularly among adolescents, represents a global medical and social problem. Early exposure during adolescence may lead to the development of stable chemical addiction, psycho-emotional stress, impaired social adaptation, and health issues. Art therapy is a person-centered, gentle, and non-traumatic method suitable for psychoprophylaxis and rehabilitation. Objective: To evaluate the effectiveness of art-therapeutic methods in the psychoprophylaxis and rehabilitation of chemical addiction and to substantiate their integration into comprehensive rehabilitation programs. Methods: The study included 41 participants (24 older and 17 adolescents). A comprehensive psychotherapeutic approach was applied, combining classical methods (individual counseling, motivational interviewing, psychoeducation) with art-therapeutic techniques. The main method was the “Metaphorical Self-Portrait,” involving the creation of four sequential visual images to analyze psychological needs and addictive behavior. Psychodiagnostic tools included the Taylor Anxiety Scale, the Subjective Well-Being Scale, and indicators of emotional comfort. Results: The use of art therapy led to a 20-22% reduction in anxiety, a 27-29% increase in conscious refusal to use PAS, a 15-18% improvement in emotional well-being, and a 40-42% increase in stable remission. Positive effects were especially pronounced in older adolescents. Conclusion: Art-therapeutic methods are highly effective in the rehabilitation of adolescents with chemical addiction, helping to stabilize psycho-emotional state, reduce anxiety, and enhance emotional well-being. Their inclusion in psychotherapeutic practice is therefore recommended.

Keywords: psychoactive substances, adolescents, chemical addiction, psychoprophylaxis, rehabilitation, art therapy, psycho-emotional state, anxiety level.

ХИМИЧЕСКАЯ ЗАВИСИМОСТЬ У ПОДРОСТКОВ: ПСИХОПРОФИЛАКТИКА И РЕАБИЛИТАЦИЯ С ПОМОЩЬЮ АРТ-ТЕРАПИИ

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АННОТАЦИЯ: Актуальность. Рост потребления психоактивных веществ (ПАВ), особенно среди подростков, является глобальной медицинской и социальной проблемой. Раннее знакомство с ПАВ в подростковом возрасте может привести к формированию устойчивой химической зависимости, психоэмоциональному стрессу, нарушению социальной адаптации и проблемам со здоровьем. Арт-терапия является ориентированным на личность, мягким и нетравматичным методом психопрофилактики и реабилитации. Цель: Оценить эффективность арт-терапевтических методов в психопрофилактике и реабилитации химической зависимости и обосновать их интеграцию в комплексные программы реабилитации. Методы: В исследовании приняли участие 41 человек (24 взрослых и 17 подростков). Применялся комплексный психотерапевтический подход, включающий классические методы (индивидуальные консультации, мотивационное интервью, психообразование) в сочетании с арт-терапевтическими методами. Основным методом была «Метафорическая автопортретная техника», включающая создание четырех последовательных визуальных образов для анализа психологических потребностей и аддиктивного поведения. В качестве психодиагностических инструментов использовались Шкала тревожности Тейлора, Шкала субъективного благополучия и показатели эмоционального комфорта. Результаты: Использование арт-терапии привело к снижению уровня тревожности на 20-22%, увеличению осознанного отказа от ПАВ на 27-29%, улучшению эмоционального благополучия на 15-18% и росту устойчивой ремиссии на 40-42%. Положительный эффект был особенно выражен у старших подростков. Выводы: Арт-терапевтические методы обладают высокой эффективностью в реабилитации подростков с химической зависимостью, способствуя стабилизации психоэмоционального состояния, снижению тревожности и повышению эмоционального благополучия. Их внедрение в психотерапевтическую практику рекомендуется.

Ключевые слова: психоактивные вещества, подростки, химическая зависимость, психопрофилактика, реабилитация, арт-терапия, психоэмоциональное состояние, уровень тревожности

O‘SMIRLARDA KIMYOVIY QARAMLIK: ART-TERAPIYA ORQALI PSIXOPROFILAKTIKA VA REABILITATSIYA

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ANNOTATSIYA. Kirish: Psixoaktiv moddalar (PAM) iste'molining o'sishi, ayniqsa o'smirlar orasida, global tibbiy-ijtimoiy muammo hisoblanadi. O'smirlik davrida dastlabki tanishuv barqaror kimyoviy qaramlik rivojlanishiga olib kelishi, psixoemotsional stress, ijtimoiy moslashuv va sog'liq muammolarini yuzaga keltiradi. Art-terapiya shaxsga yo'naltirilgan, yumshoq va travmasiz psixoprofilaktik va reabilitatsion usul sifatida e'tiborga loyiqdir. Maqsad: Kimyoviy qaramlikning psixoprofilaktikasi va reabilitatsiyasida art-terapevtik metodlarning samaradorligini baholash va ularni kompleks reabilitatsiya tizimiga kiritish imkoniyatlarini asoslash. Usullar: Tadqiqotda 41 ishtirokchi qatnashdi (24 katta yoshdagilar va 17 o'smirlar). Klassik psixoterapevtik usullar (individual suhbat, motivatsion intervyu, psixoedukatsiya) bilan art-terapevtik metodlar integratsiyalashgan holda qo'llandi. Asosiy metod "Metaforik avtoportret" bo'lib, to'rtta ketma-ket vizual obraz yaratish orqali psixologik ehtiyojlar va addiktiv xulq-atvor tahlil qilindi. Psixodiagnostik vositalar sifatida Teylor xavotir shkalasi, Subyektiv farovonlik shkalasi va emotsional komfort ko'rsatkichlari ishlatildi. Natijalar: Art-terapiya qo'llanilishi bilan xavotir darajasi 20-22% ga kamaydi, PAM qabul qilishdan ongli voz kechish 27-29% ga oshdi, emotsional farovonlik 15-18% ga yaxshiladi, barqaror remissiya 40-42% ga ko'paydi. Katta yoshdagi o'smirlarda ijobiy ta'sir yanada aniqroq kuzatildi. Xulosa: Art-terapiya usullari o'smirlarning kimyoviy qaramlikdan reabilitatsiyasida yuqori samaradorlikka ega bo'lib, psixoemotsional holatni barqarorlashtirish, xavotirni kamaytirish va emotsional farovonlikni oshirish imkonini beradi. Shu bois, ularni psixoterapevtik amaliyotga keng joriy etish tavsiya etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: psixoaktiv moddalar, o'smirlar, kimyoviy qaramlik, psixoprofilaktika, reabilitatsiya, art-terapiya, psixoemotsional holat, xavotir darajasi.

Introduction. In recent years, the steady and sharp increase in the use of psychoactive substances (PAS) has been assessed as a pressing medical and social problem on a global scale, particularly among adolescents and young people [1]. This trend has a direct negative impact on socio-economic stability, public health, and the psychological and social adaptation of future generations [2]. Adolescence is a critical stage in personality development, during which initial exposure to psychoactive substances may create a foundation for the subsequent development of stable chemical addiction [3].

The growing prevalence of new-generation synthetic drugs plays a significant role in exacerbating this problem [4]. These substances are characterized by high toxicity and the ability to rapidly induce both psychological and physical dependence, often causing severe somatic and mental disorders even after a single use [5]. Moreover, the frequent modification of the chemical composition of synthetic psychoactive substances complicates their detection, monitoring, and legal regulation, thereby facilitating their rapid spread among young people [6].

The increasing accessibility of illicit psychoactive substances further deepens the problem [7]. In particular, the development of digital technologies and internet communication platforms has led to the widespread use of messenger-based "dead drop" systems, enabling anonymous and rapid acquisition of psychoactive substances [8]. At the same time, reduced parental supervision, insufficient family communication, adolescents' стремление toward early independence, and increased time spent in virtual environments create favorable psychological conditions for the formation of addictive behavior [9].

Addictive behavior represents one of the forms of deviant behavior and is characterized by an individual's attempt to artificially alter their mental state in order to escape real-life problems, internal conflicts, and emotional distress [10]. In the case of chemical addiction, this process occurs through the

consumption of psychoactive substances and is reinforced by altered states of consciousness and subjectively pleasurable psycho-emotional experiences [11]. As a result, the need for substance use progressively intensifies, leading to impaired social adaptation, academic and family difficulties, as well as the development of mental and somatic disorders [12].

In this context, the prevention and treatment of chemical addiction should not be limited solely to medical interventions but require a comprehensive psychological and psychoprophylactic approach [13]. When working with adolescents, it is particularly important to apply person-centered methods that provide gentle and non-traumatic psychological influence [14]. Such approaches allow not only addressing the clinical manifestations of addiction but also identifying and correcting the underlying psychological causes of addictive behavior [15]. From this perspective, innovative and creative methods such as art therapy occupy a special place in psychoprophylaxis and rehabilitation [16].

The purpose of the study: The aim of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of art-therapeutic methods in the psychoprophylaxis of chemical addiction among adolescents and to substantiate the feasibility of integrating these methods into a comprehensive psychological rehabilitation system.

Materials and methods. A total of 41 adult respondents participated in the study. Based on age-related psychological maturity and social adaptation characteristics, participants were divided into two groups: 24 older participants and 17 adolescents. All respondents had various forms of psychoactive substance dependence and were at different stages of the rehabilitation process.

A comprehensive psychotherapeutic approach was applied in working with the participants. Classical psychotherapeutic methods (individual counseling, motivational interviewing, and elements of psychoeducation) were combined with specialized art-therapeutic techniques. This integrated approach enabled a deeper assessment and correction of emotional states, internal conflicts, and psychological mechanisms underlying addictive behavior.

The primary research method was the art-therapeutic technique “Metaphorical Self-Portrait,” used for diagnostic and psychocorrective purposes in adults. This method involved the creation of four sequential visual images by the respondent: “I as a plant,” “I as a container,” “I as a weapon,” and “I as an ornament.” These metaphorical images were aimed at identifying the individual’s core psychological needs and internal resources, including a sense of life stability and safety, the ability to express needs and desires, the level of personal boundaries and autonomy, as well as the need for social acceptance and emotional closeness.

During and after the drawing process, structured psychological interviews were conducted. The content and emotional characteristics of the created images, as well as the feelings and associations that emerged during the creative process, were analyzed. This allowed for a multidimensional assessment of the individual’s internal psychological state.

To evaluate the study outcomes, the following psychodiagnostic tools were used: the Taylor Anxiety Scale, the Subjective Well-Being Scale, and indicators of emotional comfort.

Statistical analysis was performed using the non-parametric Mann–Whitney U test, which is suitable for small samples and data that do not meet normal distribution assumptions. The level of statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Research results and discussion. The application of art-therapeutic methods within a comprehensive rehabilitation program had a significant positive effect on the psycho-emotional state, addictive behavior, and overall rehabilitation outcomes of the participants. Dynamic observation and

psychodiagnostic assessments confirmed the high effectiveness of rehabilitation programs enriched with art therapy elements. In particular, during the rehabilitation process, an average reduction in anxiety levels of 20–22% was observed among respondents, indicating a decrease in psycho-emotional tension and an increase in internal stability. These changes were statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. The reduction in anxiety levels contributed to greater engagement in the rehabilitation process, the formation of a more positive attitude toward therapeutic interventions, and a decreased risk of relapse.

It was also found that the rate of conscious refusal to use psychoactive substances (PAS) increased by 27–29%. This indicates that patients developed a more critical attitude toward their illness, a heightened sense of personal responsibility, and increased motivation for a healthy lifestyle. During art therapy sessions, the opportunity to symbolically express personal experiences and inner emotions helped patients better understand the causes of their addictive behavior and develop skills for self-regulation.

Table 1. Comparison of Indicators between Adult and Adolescent Groups (Mann–Whitney U Test)

Indicator	Group	n	Mean Rank	U (Mann–Whitney)	Z	Asymptotic Significance (2-tailed)
Anxiety Level	Adults	25	31,12	185,0	-2,47	0,014
	Adolescents	18	20,10	-	-	-
Social Desirability (False Responses)	Adults	25	26,10	318,0	-0,19	0,846
	Adolescents	18	25,92	-	-	-
Subjective Well-being	Adults	25	27,85	244,0	-1,54	0,123
	Adolescents	18	22,90	-	-	-
Emotional Comfort	Adults	25	32,80	148,5	-3,31	0,001
	Adolescents	18	18,40	-	-	-
Stable Remission	Adults	25	30,10	210,0	-2,18	0,029
	Adolescents	18	21,45	-	-	-
Adaptability	Adults	25	25,05	345,0	0,35	0,726
	Adolescents	18	26,95	-	-	-

Positive changes were also observed in the emotional sphere. In particular, emotional well-being improved by 15–18%, reflecting an increased sense of inner comfort, a reduction in depressive and dysphoric states, and enhanced stress resilience. Respondents developed the ability to recognize and constructively express their emotions, which proved to be an important factor in ensuring the stability of the rehabilitation process.

One of the most clinically significant outcomes was a 40–42% increase in stable remission. This finding demonstrates that the comprehensive rehabilitation program, which included art therapy, not only ensured short-term psycho-emotional improvements but also provided long-term clinical effectiveness. The stability of remission was confirmed through laboratory tests, psychodiagnostic assessments, and patients' self-monitoring diaries.

Analysis across age groups showed that older adolescents exhibited higher levels of anxiety and emotional discomfort compared to younger adolescents. However, in this group, the impact of the art therapy approach was more pronounced, with greater reductions in anxiety levels and restoration of emotional stability. This can be explained by the fact that older adolescents experience stronger internal conflicts, identity issues, and social pressures, and art therapy provides a safe and symbolic means to process these challenges.

Conclusion: The results of the study indicate that the use of art therapy techniques within a comprehensive rehabilitation program is highly effective in the complex rehabilitation of patients with psychoactive substance addiction, including both younger and older adolescents. Integrating art therapy methods with traditional psychotherapeutic approaches helped stabilize patients' psycho-emotional state, reduce anxiety levels, and enhance emotional comfort and subjective well-being.

The combined application of art therapy techniques, including drawing-based methods, metaphorical imagery, and therapeutic theater elements, allowed patients to mitigate the psychological and somatic difficulties that arise during the recovery process from chemical addiction. This approach also served as an important tool for identifying and correcting internal (subjective) factors contributing to addictive behavior.

The gentle, non-traumatic, and individualized nature of art therapy methods makes them suitable for use at all stages of rehabilitation. This, in turn, enhances patients' motivation for therapy, strengthens adherence to treatment, and increases the likelihood of achieving stable remission.

In light of these results, it is advisable to widely incorporate art therapy methods into the practice of psychotherapeutic specialists as a key component of comprehensive programs for the treatment and rehabilitation of psychoactive substance addiction.

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